

Improving forecasts for *Karenia brevis* in the Gulf of Mexico

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Abstract

Brevetoxins produced by *Karenia brevis* can be aerosolized and lead to severe respiratory irritation, with documented health risks for people with asthma. Economic impacts also occur as even healthy people avoid beach businesses when a “red tide” is reported to be in a region. However, the distribution of brevetoxin aerosol impact varies greatly, depending on patchiness of blooms and wind speed and direction. Locating and forecasting the blooms and respiratory risk are then necessary to reduce health and economic impacts. Previously, manual and qualitative evaluation determined the location and respiratory risk of these blooms at coarse resolutions (daily and county scale). The forecast has substantially been improved for nowcast timeliness with an automated capability that combines new resources and models. These include a chlorophyll-a fluorescence algorithm applied to Sentinel-3 satellite products, the HABscope (a microscope deployed by volunteers with digital video analysis), existing water sampling networks, improved weather forecasts, respiratory irritation risk models, and a bloom intensification forecast.

Keywords: brevetoxins, aerosols, asthma, forecast, HABscope, *Karenia brevis*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7033205>

Introduction

Karenia brevis toxic aerosols have significant human health impacts, particularly in people with asthma (Fleming *et al.*, 2005a, 2005b, 2007, 2009, 2011; Kirkpatrick *et al.*, 2006, 2011). These aerosols also lead to significant economic impacts resulting from the cost of associated medical visits and from reductions in tourism when people avoid beaches (Hoagland *et al.*, 2009). With insufficient information and notification on respiratory risk, the potential for health issues increases. Although *Karenia brevis* blooms, which are locally termed “red tides”, can extend significant distances along and offshore of coastal regions, respiratory irritation is often quite variable from day to day and beach to beach. This variability is caused by a combination of patchiness in the cell density combined with shifts in wind from onshore to offshore (Stumpf *et al.*, 2009). Fig.1 illustrates the variability of winds between morning and afternoon. In 2004, a twice weekly Gulf of Mexico Harmful Algal Bloom (HAB) forecast was launched by NOAA to provide more warning of bloom impacts at county beaches. A validation study found that the forecast of respiratory irritation somewhere in the county was correct over 70% of the days (for example, if a forecast of high risk of irritation was made, it did occur somewhere in the county), however, when applied to individual beaches, the forecast was correct only 20% of the time (Stumpf *et al.*, 2009). With lack of detailed information, there is exposure risk to those with chronic respiratory illness. They may visit a beach when toxins are present. Also, those who have experienced even minimal “red tide” symptoms are likely to assume that all beaches are not safe and avoid them and coastal businesses. Our goal is to

provide sufficient resolution to protect the health and economy of the community.

Fig. 1. Difference in frequency of offshore (left) and onshore (right) winds between morning (dark in front) and afternoon (light in back) (Stumpf *et al.*, 2009).

The goal of this project is to provide beach level forecasts in 3-hour time intervals with updates that are fully automated like a weather report. Providing frequent updates due to changing conditions allows beach goers to make informed decisions regarding their exposure to toxic *K. brevis* aerosols.

Material and Methods

To achieve these goals, we employed a combination of 21st century technologies.

Improved satellite data

We use the Sentinel-3, Ocean Land Colour Instrument (OLCI), launched in 2016 by the Copernicus program. OLCI has a 300 m pixel resolution and provides six images per week. Previous satellites (Terra and Aqua) offered 1 km pixels, an order of magnitude lower areal resolution, and no information within about 2 km (pixels) of the shore. OLCI allows a better ‘snapshot’ of the bloom that can aid

decision making on where water sampling efforts should occur. An example of the improved detail is shown in Fig. 2.

HABscope

To improve the spatial and temporal resolution of water samples and cell counts, we developed the HABscope. This instrument employs an easy-to-use microscope combined with an iPod touch tablet computer (Fig. 3). The iPod is set on the microscope using a 3D printed mount. In lieu of the traditional method of manually counting cells, a short video of the water sample is captured, and uploaded to a GCOOS (Gulf of Mexico Coastal Ocean Observing System) portal where an image analysis algorithm automatically identifies, tracks, and counts the live cells (Hardison *et al.*, 2019). The ease of use of the HABscope has allowed a citizen science network to be established to provide a substantial increase in the frequency and spatial extent of monitoring for *K. brevis* abundance. The forecast ingests cellular abundance from both HABscope and traditional monitoring.

Higher resolution weather models and forecasts

Our third step in this improved forecast involves the use of higher resolution wind forecasts (available through the National Digital Forecast Database, NDFD, at digital.weather.gov) and determines the beach orientation relative to the wind forecast. NDFD has hourly 2.5 km resolution, which became operational in 2014. Fig. 4 illustrates a graphical display of wind orientation against the shoreline in the vicinity of Tampa Bay. The combination of wind direction with cell counts is used in a model of respiratory forecast risk (Stumpf *et al.*, 2009)

Fig. 2. Example imagery from Sentinel-3 OLCI of a *Karenia brevis* bloom along southwest Florida, U.S.A., 19 Aug 2021. The inset shows the lower resolution data from Terra satellite, which was previously used. Note lack of data (gray) in Terra.

Fig. 3. HABscope.

Fig. 4: Example NDFD wind direction.

Fig. 5. Previous Gulf of Mexico HAB Bulletin.

Results and Discussion

The results of these efforts are a significant improvement in the resolution compared to the 2004 Gulf of Mexico HAB Bulletin. Instead of a general statement of daily risk across all county beaches, individual beaches are forecasted at 3-hour intervals throughout the day. Beachgoers then select the location and/or the time of their beach visit, allowing them to minimize their risk of exposure to the toxic *Karenia* aerosols. Fig. 5 shows a forecast map from the previous HAB Bulletin. Only the county that is impacted is highlighted. In Figs. 6 (4 pm) and 7 (10 pm), we show the new forecast which demonstrates the spatial variability from beach to beach and the temporal variability from 3-hour windows within the same day.

The respiratory forecast, hosted by GCOOS, and the improved remote sensing products, produced by NOAA, is a demonstration of the improved HAB products that can be produced through multi-partner projects. The forecasts will expand to the Texas coast as needed. To date, we have had over 200,000 visits to the site, primarily from the US but also a large number from Canada and Europe. We believe these products will allow residents and visitors to make informed decisions regarding their beach visits during *K. brevis* blooms.

Fig. 6. New GoMex HAB Respiratory Forecast, 4 pm forecast.

Fig. 7. New GoMex HAB Respiratory Forecast, 10 pm the same day as Fig. 6.

Fig. 8. New Gulf of Mexico HAB Forecast site.

Acknowledgements. We want to acknowledge and thank the enormous sampling effort by our dedicated HABscope community partners and volunteers who have made this project possible. This work was supported by NOAA Internal funding, NOAA NCCOS MERHAB NA20NOS4780194, the US Integrated Ocean Observing Program (US IOOS) and NASA Applied Sciences Health and Air Quality, ROSES NN13ZDA001. Reference to any specific commercial product does not constitute or imply endorsement or recommendation by the United States Government.

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